

The Use of Possession Markers in Bahasa Bakumpai

A Generative Morphology Study

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Abstract

This research is about the morphological process which occurs when a Bakumpai speakers combine nouns and possession markers. The theory applied in this research is generative morphology. The object of this research is bahasa Bakumpai, one of the languages used by people in South and Central Borneo who live by Barito River. The data collection was conducted by collecting nouns and the possession markers exist in bahasa Bakumpai from researcher himself and clarified by other Bakumpai speakers. Result of the research shows that there are some suffixes that used as the singular possession markers: *-kuh*, *-m*, *-e*, and some morphemes for plural such as *iki*, *awen*, *itah*, and *ketuh* and when those markers are attached to the nouns there are some processes occurs which are described by using word and paradigm approach.

Keywords: *Generative Morphology, word and paradigm, morpheme, root, suffix*

A. INTRODUCTION

Borneo is one of islands in Indonesia with lots of cultures with unique characteristics of each. As we know that every culture has their own language as means for the people to communicate each other, meaning that the language enables them to interact and share many things and so is in Borneo. As a big island, we know that this island is rich of tribes, cultures and languages. Every tribes has a unique language used in their daily life and one of the tribes exists in Borneo is Dayak Bakumpai which is known as a tribe whose religion is Islam. As most of people of a tribe who depend on river as the source of the most important need of life, the people of this tribe live by the Barito River which lies on South Borneo and

Central Borneo, from Marabahan (as the central of the tribe) that is located in South Borneo until Puruk Cahu that is located in Central Borneo¹.

This tribe, as other cultures, has a language used to interact by the people called Bahasa Bakumpai. In Bahasa Bakumpai, there are some words or lexemes which becomes root of words and these words may have new meanings when they are adjoined with morphemes or affixes. There are so many variations of morphemes combination in this language and one of the morphemes that can be combined is affix of possession markers. This affix is attached in two ways: first it is attached directly to the root of noun without any spaces and second it is added to the root with a space or separated from the root. This variation occurs when the noun belongs to more than one person (your, their, and ours). Since this is a language used by people in villages, not many people know about how this language system is. Therefore researcher is interested to analyze and introduce one of greatness exist in Indonesia in form of the language of this culture to the world of linguistics. In this paper, researcher focuses on the morphological processes in the combination of noun root and the affixes of possession markers.

B. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this research are as below:

- a. to analyze morphological process in the attachment of possessions markers to the noun root, and
- b. to describe the morphological process by using word and paradigm approach.

C. THEORITICAL FRAME

a. Generative Morphology

When we hear the word ‘morphology’, we will have question in our mind: “What is Morphology?” well, straight to the point, Morphology is the study of word formation, including the ways new words are coined in the languages of the world, and the way forms of words are varied depending on how they’re used in sentences (Lieber, 2009). Morphology itself is used for different reasons, depends on the need we have. One of the reasons for having morphology is to form new lexemes from old ones. It can change the part of speech (or category) of a word, for example, turning verbs into nouns or

¹ (<http://baritobasin.wordpress.com/2008/03/31/who-are-the-bakumpai/>) and (<http://www.disbudpar.baritoselatankab.go.id/2012/04/19/suku-dayak-bakumpai/>)

adjectives, or nouns into adjectives, On the other hand, we sometimes use morphology even when we don't need new lexemes. For example, we saw that each lexeme can have a number of word forms. The lexeme WALK has forms like *walk*, *walks*, *walked*, *walking* that can be used in different grammatical contexts.

One of theories known by linguist talking about morphology is transformational generative suggested by Chomsky. Principles of generative morphology, according to Chomsky, generally can be described in some explanation.

First, generative morphology is a theory about competence which refers to the knowledge owned by native speaker about his own language and not about performance which refers to the use of language in daily life of the native speaker. Generative morphology is based on competence and not performance because linguistic theory is created to find the mental realization that becomes basic of someone's behavior.

Second, language is creative and innovative, meaning a speaker can create various and new sentences, understand them and analyze the acceptance of those sentences in daily life.

Third, generative morphology is a tool to analyze and formulate the rule of forming a sentence, interpreting the sentence, and pronouncing it.

Fourth, language is the mirror of one's thought, meaning that language help people to understand others' thought. (Ba'dulu and Herman: 2004)

b. Morpheme

When we are writing or speaking, we use words which can be segmented into smaller segment. For example is in speaking which can be segmented into smaller parts, 'speak' and 'ing'. These small parts are what we call "morpheme". Simply, morpheme can be said as the smallest meaningful constituents in a certain linguistic expression. Morpheme itself can be divided into two types: free and bound morpheme. Free morpheme is independent morpheme, meaning that this type of morpheme has clear and concrete meaning without being combined with other morphemes. The examples are book, bag, speak, walk, small, big, well, and right. Bound morpheme is the vice versa of free, meaning that this type of morpheme does not have clear meaning until it is attached to free morphemes. The ones included in this type are in form of affixations such as '-ing', 's', '-es', '-ed', '-ful', and other affixations. (Booij: 2005)

c. Root

When a speaker use words in daily life, he sometimes says or writes words which contain more than one morphemes like in 'unintentionally'. These words can be segmented into smaller part, bound and

free morphemes. The segmented free morpheme that cannot be analyzed further into constituent morphemes is what we call root. In word 'unintentionally' we can have 'un-', 'intend', '-ion', '-al', and '-ly'. The free morpheme 'intend' is the root since it cannot be segmented anymore. (Booij: 2005)

d. Prefix, Infix, and Suffix

As has been stated above, there is morphemes that called affix which will have concrete meaning if they are attached to free morphemes. There are three kinds of affix which each are classified or named based on the position of the attachment. When the affix is attached in the front of the base or root, it is what we call prefix. i.e. *imperfect*, *undone*, *disagree*. When the affix is attached in the middle of the root or base, that is infix. i.e. *gerigi* and *gemilang*. Suffix is the affix which is attached at the end of the root or base like in *readable*, *activity*, and *movement*. (Booij: 2005)

e. Approaches in analyzing morphological rules

When a researcher analyzes the morphological process, one of goals is to find the regularity or generalization of the rules which are applied in a certain language. There are three approach which can be conducted to find this generalization, they are "Item and arrangement" which focuses on the arrangement of morphemes in a morph, "Item and process" which focuses on the morphophonemic of the morph, and the last one which is used in this paper is "Word and paradigm" which focuses on how the new lexeme are created in a specific language. The chosen approach is Word and Paradigm approach or also called word based model since it has the ability to analyze the fundamental or significance of the word emphasized and the relationship between complex words by formulating word-schemas that represent the common features of sets of morphologically related words (Haspelmath, 2002).

D. RESEARCH METHOD

In this research, the researcher collected the data by listing nouns and the morphemes of possession markers exist in bahasa Bakumpai. Since the researcher himself is a native speaker of bahasa Bakumpai, he wrote the list of the nouns and the affixes which are attached to the noun and confirmed the list to the other native speakers of bahasa Bakumpai in Muara Teweh. From a lot of words in the list, researched chose 11 words which have different characteristics at the ending of them as samples words which represented the environments where the morphological process happened. The samples were then classified based on the suffixes attached to the root and additional morphemes until researcher got the groups of words from which there could be taken generalization of attachment rules. After putting those verbs in groups, researcher analyzed the variations of attachment and formulated general rules based on

the similarities in the attachment of the suffixes to the root. To analyze the morphological process, researcher chose Word and Paradigm approach to analyze the data since it is appropriate for complex word formations, therefore he could see the processes of the attachments in detail (Haspelmath: 2002). Finally, from the description researcher got conclusion about how the rules to attach the suffixes and morphemes of possession markers to the noun root.

E. FINDING

When researcher collected nouns attached by possession markers, there is fact that shows if the ending sounds of the words affect on how the markers attached. Based on the data found in the field, researcher chose eleven words which are all root of nouns with various ending that will affect the attachment of the suffix. The sample words are as seen in the table below:

N Root	meaning	Ending of words
Kula	Brother	a
Kumpa	Pump	a
Sapida	Bike	a
Karamba	Fish cage	a
Tatamba	Medicine	a
Papati	Weakness	i
Guti	Louse	i
Nupi	Dream	i
Kupi	Coffee	i
Biti	People	i
Buku	Book	u
Timbaku	Unique vegeta	u
Silu	Nail	u
Siku	Elbow	u
Sawe	Wife	e
Luwe	Swamp	e
Kunge	Body	e
Mate	Eye	e
Nyame	Mouth	u
Pai	Foot	ai
Bua	Fruit	ua
Parei	Rice	ei
Balau	Hair	au
Tapah	Fish (tapah)	Consonant
Behas	Rice	Consonant

Jukung	Boat	Consonant
Salawar	Trousers	Consonant
Takuluk	Head	Consonant
Galas	Glass	Consonant
Caramin	Mirror	Consonant
Tupi	Cap	Consonant
Sadurung	Veil	Consonant

On the sample shown above, we can see that there are three variations of ending in bahasa Bakumpai nouns: vowels (a, i, u e), diphthongs (ai, ua, ei, au) and consonants. As has been stated in introduction, when a Bakumpai speaker wants to tell the possession of a noun there are two ways he uses: first, if the owner of the noun is singular he will add suffix to the noun and second, if the owner is plural he will use separated morpheme after the root. If the speaker uses the plural possession markers, there is also process where he has to add a sound at the end of certain noun before he continues to say the morpheme of possession markers. There are three suffixes showing the possession of a noun in bahasa Bakumpai. They are:

- a. '-kuh' (my)
- b. '-m' (your, singular)
- c. '-e' (their)

And the additional morphemes are:

- d. 'iki' (our-speaker included, hearer excluded)
- e. 'awen' (their)
- f. 'itah' (our-speaker and hearer included)
- g. 'ketuh' (your, plural)

Every ending will affect the suffixes attached to the words and how the effects are can be seen in the explanation below, but there are only few words which represent different endings taken as sample to give detail in the process.

SUFFIX AS SINGULAR POSSESSION MARKER

A. Suffix '-kuh'

N Root	meaning	ending	morfem /-kuh/	process
Kula	Brother	a	Kulaŋkuh	(+ŋ) +kuh
Papati	Weakness	i	Papatiŋkuh	(+ŋ) +kuh
Buku	Book	u	Bukuŋkuh	(+ŋ) +kuh
Sawe	Wife	e	Sawaŋkuh	(e->a) (+ŋ) +kuh
Pai	Foot	ai	Paiŋkuh	(+ŋ) +kuh
Bua	Fruit	ua	Buaŋkuh	(+ŋ) +kuh
Parei	Rice	ei	Parei kuh	+kuh
Balau	Hair	au	Balau kuh	+kuh
Tapah	Fish (tapah)	Consonant	Tapah kuh	+kuh
Behas	Rice	Consonant	Behas kuh	+kuh
Jukung	Boat	Consonant	Jukuŋkuh	+kuh

According to the data shown in the table above, researcher can conclude that when the root ends with consonants and diphthong [ei] and [au], the suffix is attached directly but for other endings such as vowels and diphthongs [ai] and [ua], speakers of this language will add sound [ŋ] before attaching the suffix.

The rules can be seen as below:

a. /XV/ → /XVŋkuh/

(If root ends with vowels, add [ŋkuh] to the root)

Example: Iye nah **kulaŋkuh** (Dia adalah saudaraku).

b. /Xai/ → /Xaiŋkuh/

(If root ends with diphthong [ai], add [ŋkuh] to the root)

Example: Kapehe **paiŋkuh** tuh (My foot is hurt).

c. /Xua/ → /Xuaŋkuh/

(If root ends with diphthong [ua], add [ŋkuh] to the root)

Example: Ela indinu **buaŋkuh** hikau! (Please don't take my fruit!)

B. Suffix '-m'

N Root	meaning	ending	Morfem /-m/	process
Kula	Brother	a	Kulam	+m
Papati	Weakness	i	Papatim	+m
Buku	Book	u	Bukum	+m
Sawe	Wife	e	Sawam	(e->a) +m
Pai	Foot	ai	Paim	+m
Bua	Fruit	ua	Buaum	(+u) +m
Parei	Rice	ei	Pareium	(+u) +m
Balau	Hair	au	Balaum	+m
Tapah	Fish (tapah)	Consonant	Tapahum	(+u) +m
Behas	Rice	Consonant	Behasum	(+u) +m
Jukung	Boat	Consonant	Jukungum	(+u) +m

As can be seen in the data shown in the table above, researcher can conclude for this suffix that when the root ends with vowels, diphthongs [ai] and [au], the suffix is attached directly but for other endings such as consonants and diphthongs [ei] and [ua], speakers of this language will add sound [u] before attaching the suffix.

The rules can be seen as below:

a. /XC/ → /XC_{um}/

(If root ends with consonants, add [um] to the root)

Example: Tenga ie **behasum** hikau (Give him your rice).

b. /Xei/ → /Xei_{um}/

(If root ends with diphthong [ei], add [um] to the root)

Pire kilu ehat **pareium** nah we? (How much does your rice weigh?)

c. /Xua/ → /Xua_{um}/

(If root ends with diphthong [ua], add [um] to the root)

Ancap kinan **buaum** hikau! (Eat your fruit quickly!)

C. Suffix '-e'

N Root	meaning	Ending	Morfem /-e/	process
Kula	Brother	a	Kulaie	(+i) +e
Papati	Weakness	i	Papatie	+e
Buku	Book	u	Bukuie	(+i) +e
Sawe	Wife	e	Sawaie	(e->ai) +e
Pai	Foot	ai	Paie	+e
Bua	Fruit	ua	Buae	+e
Parei	Rice	ei	Pareie	+e
Balau	Hair	au	Balauie	+e
Tapah	Fish (tapah)	Consonant	Tapahie	+e
Behas	Rice	Consonant	Behasie	+e
Jukung	Boat	Consonant	Jukungie	+e

Like other suffixations, this suffix also have some rules to apply. The rules are that almost all of the root will be directly attached by the suffix but when the root ends with vowels [a], [u] and [e], the suffix will be attached after add sound [i].

The rules can be seen as below:

a. /Xa/ → /Xa_{ie}/

(If root ends with [a], add [ie] to the root)

Ji mahanggap baju bahenda te nah **kulaie** (The man in white clothes there is his brother).

b. /Xu/ → /Xu_{ie}/

(If root ends with [u], add [ie] to the root)

Bukum lah jikau nah? (Is that your book?)

c. /Xe/ → /Xe_{ie}/

(If root ends with [e], change the sound [e] to [a] and add [ie] to the root)

Bahalap banar **sawaie** te nah lah (His wife is so beautiful).

MORPHEME AS PLURAL POSSESSION MARKERS

Based on the analysis conducted by researcher, he found that for the plural markers there are some similarities to show the possession of nouns. Firstly, when the root ends with consonants and diphthongs [ei] and [au], they just say the morphemes after the noun. Secondly, when the root ends with vowel and diphthongs [ai] and [ua], they will add [-n] to the root and then say the morphemes. Thirdly, when the

root ends with [e], they will replace the sound [e] with [a] and add sound [n] before saying the morphemes of possession markers.

The rule can be formulated as below:

- a. /XV/ → /XV_n/
(If root ends with vowels, add [n] to the root)
Ji kanih nah **kulan** iki (He is our brother).
- b. /Xai/ → /Xai_n/
(If root ends with diphthong [ai], add [n] to the root)
Kapehe **pain** awen buah sepak e (Their feet are hurt because he hit them).
- c. /Xua/ → /Xua_n/
(If root ends with diphthong [ua], add [n] to the root)
Hai-hai **buan** iki si lebu kanih nah (Our fruits at village are big).
- d. /Xe/ → /Xe_n/
(If root ends with sound [e], replace [e] with [a] and then add [n] to the root)
Lamun ketuh tulak, **sawan** ketuh umba kia mingkehe? (If all of you are going somewhere, your wives are coming with you, aren't they?)

The words and processes of adding possession marker with plural owners of noun can be seen in the tables below:

D. Morpheme 'iki'

Root	meaning	Ending	morfem /iki/	process
Kula	Brother	a	Kulan iki	(+n) +iki
Papati	Weakness	i	Papatin iki	(+n) +iki
Buku	Book	u	Bukun iki	(+n) +iki
Sawe	Wife	e	Sawan iki	(e->a) (+n) +iki
Pai	Foot	ai	Pain iki	(+n) +iki
Bua	Fruit	ua	Buan iki	(+n) +iki
Parei	Rice	ei	Parei iki	+ iki
Balau	Hair	au	Balau iki	+iki
Tapah	Fish (tapah)	Consonant	Tapah iki	+iki
Behas	Rice	Consonant	Behas iki	+iki
Jukung	Boat	Consonant	Jukung iki	+ iki

E. Morpheme 'awen'

N Root	meaning	Ending	morfem /awen/	Process
Kula	Brother	a	Kulan awen	(+n) +awen
Papati	Weakness	i	Papatin awen	(+n) +awen
Buku	Book	u	Bukun awen	(+n) +awen
Sawe	Wife	e	Sawan awen	(e->a) (+n) +awen
Pai	Foot	ai	Pain awen	(+n) +awen
Bua	Fruit	ua	Buan awen	(+n) +awen
Parei	Rice	ei	Parei awen	+awen
Balau	Hair	au	Balau awen	+awen
Tapah	Fish (tapah)	Consonant	Tapah awen	+awen
Behas	Rice	Consonant	Behas awen	+awen
Jukung	Boat	Consonant	Jukung awen	+awen

F. Morpheme 'itah'

N Root	meaning	Ending	morfem /itah/	Process
Kula	Brother	a	Kulan itah	(+n) +itah
Papati	Weakness	i	Papatin itah	(+n) +itah
Buku	Book	u	Bukun itah	(+n) +itah
Sawe	Wife	e	Sawan awen	(e->a) (+n) +itah
Pai	Foot	ai	Pain itah	(+n) +itah
Bua	Fruit	ua	Buan itah	(+n) +itah
Parei	Rice	ei	Parei itah	+itah
Balau	Hair	au	Balau itah	+itah
Tapah	Fish (tapah)	Consonant	Tapah itah	+itah
Behas	Rice	Consonant	Behas itah	+itah
Jukung	Boat	Consonant	Jukung itah	+itah

G. Morpheme 'ketuh'

N Root	meaning	Ending	morfem /ketuh/	Process
Kula	Brother	a	Kulan ketuh	(+n) + ketuh
Papati	Weakness	i	Papatin ketuh	(+n) + ketuh
Buku	Book	u	Bukun ketuh	(+n) + ketuh
Sawe	Wife	e	Sawan ketuh	(e->a) (+n) + ketuh
Pai	Foot	ai	Pain ketuh	(+n) + ketuh

Bua	Fruit	ua	Buan ketuh	(+n) + ketuh
Parei	Rice	ei	Parei ketuh	+ ketuh
Balau	Hair	au	Balau ketuh	+ ketuh
Tapah	Fish (tapah)	Consonant	Tapah ketuh	+ ketuh
Behas	Rice	Consonant	Behas ketuh	+ ketuh
Jukung	Boat	Consonant	Jukung ketuh	+ ketuh

F. CONCLUSION

From the data analysis conducted on the possession markers in bahasa Bakumpai, researcher can make conclusion as below:

- A. The morphological process of affixation to show possession in bahasa Bakumpai contains suffixes and morphophonemic process at once that makes Item and arrangement and Item and Process cannot be applied to analyze this kind of data, therefore Word and Paradigm is chosen as the approach.
- B. There are two groups of ways in showing possession of noun in bahasa bakumpai: group of singular owner and group of plural owners.
- C. When a speaker of bahasa Bakumpai wants to show the possession of singular owner, he will attach suffix to the root.
- D. When a speaker of bahasa Bakumpai want to show possession of plural owners, he will use the separated morphemes. But it must be noted that the ending sound of noun will affect the use of the morphemes since to use those morphemes along with certain sound, the speaker will have to add sound [n] to the root before saying the morpheme of possession markers.

Bibliography

Ba'dulu, A.M. & Herman. 2004. *Morfosintaksis*. PT. Rineka Cipta.

Booij, G. 2005. *The Grammar of Words*. Oxford University Press.

Haspelmath, M. 2002. *Understanding Morphology*. Oxford University Press.

Lieber, R. 2009. *Introducing Morphology*. Cambridge University Press.

Barito Basin. 2013. *Who are the Bakumpai?* <http://baritobasin.wordpress.com/2008/03/31/who-are-the-bakumpai/> [30 November 2103]

DISBUDPAR Barito Selatan. 2013. Suku Dayak Bakumpai.

<http://www.disbudpar.baritoselatankab.go.id/2012/04/19/suku-dayak-bakumpai/> [30 November 2013]